

HEalth diagnosis tool for **R** the **gO**lang ecosystem

ICSE 2021 Technical Track, ID#163 "Hero: On the Chaos When PATH Meets Modules" [\[Link\]](#)

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Project description

Hero is developed as an online tool (<http://www.hero-go.com/>) to help Golang developers deal with dependency management (DM) issues, by automatically diagnosing their root causes and customizing fixing suggestions.

Its main features are: 1) constructing and visualizing a **dependency model** for a Golang project under test; Specially, the dependency model shows the dependency relationships among the client project's downstream and upstream projects and their corresponding library-referencing modes; 2) **diagnosing** DM issues; 3) providing their detailed **root causes** and customized **fixing solutions** with analyses of potential benefits and consequences incurring to the ecosystem if certain fixing solutions are taken. For more detailed information, please refer to the "ABOUT" page of Hero.

Background

Ever since its first release in 2009, the Go programming language (Golang) has been well received by software communities. A major reason for its success is the powerful support of its library-based development, where a Golang project can be conveniently built on top of other projects by referencing them as libraries. As Golang evolves, it recommends the use of a new library-referencing mode (**Go Modules**) to overcome limitations of its earlier one (**GOPATH**). While these two library modes are incompatible, both are supported by the Golang ecosystem.

The mixed uses of library-referencing modes across different Golang projects have caused numerous DM issues, incurring various reference inconsistencies and even build failures. On the other hand, as observed in our empirical study, diagnosing DM issues for a Golang project is, however, a challenging task, which requires up-to-date knowledge of its upstream and downstream projects, as well as that of their possible mixed uses of the two library-referencing modes. Such knowledge is generally unavailable. Moreover, locally resolving a DM issue in a Golang project in a holistic way without considering its possible impact to the whole ecosystem can easily cause more unexpected issues to its downstream projects, which would compromise what have been benefited from the current issue resolution. To address the above challenges, we develop Hero to help Golang developers combat DM issues.

◆ **Why mixed dependency management modes among Golang projects can cause DM issues?**

Prior to Golang 1.11, library referencing was supported by the GOPATH mode. Libraries referenced by a project are fetched using command `go get`. This mode does not require developers to provide any configuration file. It

works by matching the URLs of the site hosting referenced libraries with the import paths specified by the `go get` command. However, it fetches only a library's latest version. To overcome this restriction, developers use third-party tools such as *Dep*¹ and *Glide*² to manage different library versions under the *Vendor directory*³. To satisfy developers' need for referencing specific library versions, in August 2018, Golang 1.11 introduced the Go Modules mode, which allows multiple library versions to be referenced by a module using different paths. A *module* comprises a tree of Golang source files with a `go.mod` configuration file defined in the tree's root directory. The configuration file explicitly specifies the module's dependencies with specific library versions as well as a module path by which the module itself can be uniquely referenced by other projects. The file must be specified according to the *semantic import versioning (SIV)* rules. For instance, projects whose major versions are *v2* or above, should include a version suffix like `"/v2"` at the end of their module paths.

However, as of June 2020, only 35.9% projects had migrated to Go Modules, while the rest 64.1% were still using GOPATH, resulting in the coexistence of two different library-referencing modes. Many projects suffered from various DM issues caused by such mixed library-referencing modes. To easy discuss the root causes of DM issues, we refer to the capability of recognizing a virtual path ended with a version suffix like `"/v2"` from projects in Go Modules, as *module-awareness*. Module-awareness is important for referencing libraries in the Golang ecosystem. Table 1 shows the module-awareness in different Golang versions. As we can see, a project is *module-aware* if and only if it uses a compatible or new Golang version and does not use any DM tools (tools like Dep, Glide, etc. can block the module-awareness of projects); a project is *module-unaware* if and only if it uses a legacy Golang version, or it uses a compatible or new Golang version with a DM tool.

Table 1. example Golang projects with four types of DM issues

Category	Go Version range	Mode	Using tools (dep,glide...)	Module-awareness
Legacy Golang versions	[1.0.1, 1.9.7) ∪ [1.10.1, 1.10.3)	GOPATH	✓	✗
			✗	✗
Compatible Golang versions	[1.9.7, 1.10.1) ∪ [1.10.3, 1.11.1)	GOPATH	✓	✗
			✗	✓
New Golang versions	≥ 1.11	GOPATH	✓	✗
			✗	✓
		Go Modules	—	✓

Figure 1. Comparison of module-aware and module-unaware projects

Figure 1 shows how module-aware and module-unaware projects differ in parsing an import path with or without a `"/v2"` version suffix. For an import path like `"github.com/user/projectA"`, a module-aware project could reference a specific version `v0.**` or `v1.**` of *projectA* under *v2* (latest version under *v2*, by default), while a module-unaware project would reference the version on *projectA*'s main branch (typically the latest version). While for an import path like `"github.com/user/projectA/v2"`, a module-aware project could reference a specific version `v2.**` of *projectA* (latest version under *v3*, by default), while a module-unaware project would fail to recognize it. As

1. <https://github.com/golang/dep> 2. <https://github.com/Masterminds/glide> 3. The *Vendor* attribute allows a Golang project to reference a library's different versions and keep them in different folders under a vendor directory.

discussed above, different import path interpretations by the two modes are the main causes of DM issues.

◆ **What types of DM issues can Hero deal with?**

Hero can diagnose the following three types of DM issues for a given Golang project:

- **Type A:** DM issues can occur when projects in GOPATH depend on projects in Go Modules.

As shown in Figure 2, build errors can occur when a project (A) in GOPATH with no module-awareness directly or transitively depends on a project (C) in Go Modules, but cannot recognize its virtual paths with v2+ version suffixes.

Figure 2. An illustrative example of Type A DM issue

- **Type B issues:** DM issues can occur when projects in Go Modules depend on projects in GOPATH.

A project that has migrated to Go Modules may not find their referenced libraries in GOPATH, or may fetch the unintended library versions, due to different import path interpretations by the two modes. There are following two cases:

- **Type B.1:** As shown in Figure 3, suppose that project A in Go Modules depend on project B in GOPATH, and B further depend on project C in Go Modules with import path "C/pkg". It should be noted that project C has released a v2+ version. From B's perspective, it interprets the import path as C's latest version (i.e., v2+ version on C's main branch). However, in A's build environment, the import path is interpreted as a v0/v1 version of C (no version suffix in the path). As a result, project A fails to fetch C's correct version and can encounter errors when building with B.

Figure 3. An illustrative example of Type B.1 DM issue

- **Type B.2:** As shown in Figure 4, suppose that project A in Go Modules depend on project B in GOPATH, and B further depend on project C, which is managed in B's Vendor directory. However, in project A's build environment, it references C by import path "C/pkg" declared in B's source files rather than from B's Vendor directory. Although the build may work for the time being, project A can fail to fetch C if C is deleted or moved to another repository (e.g., renaming). Even if the fetching is successful, the version on C's hosting site could be different from the one in B's Vendor directory, causing potential build errors due to the inconsistency.

Figure 4. An illustrative example of Type B.2 DM issue

- **Type C:** DM issues can occur when projects in **Go Modules** depend on projects also in **Go Modules** but not following SIV rules.

There are three cases: 1) lacking version suffixes like `"/v2"` in module paths or import paths, although the versions of concerned projects are `v2+`; 2) version tags not following the [semantic version format](#); 3) module paths in `go.mod` files are inconsistent with the URLs associated with concerned projects on their hosting sites.

Recommended browser

The recommended browser is Chrome (version 79.0.3945.130 and higher).

Artifact Evaluation

◆ Download

The artifact of Hero, `Hero.zip`, is available at <http://www.hero-go.com/artifacts>. Please first download the package, to verify the results.

◆ Inside the package

The major components in the package `Hero.zip` are described as follows:

- `20k Subjects Info.xlsx` : 20k subjects' information used in RQ1;
- `Empirical Study Dataset.xlsx` : 151 DM issues collected for RQ2&3;
- `Benchmark Dataset` folder : 132 subjects with real issues and script files used for verifying the experimental results in RQ4.

◆ An introduction to the evaluation of Hero

One can evaluate our work based on the following descriptions.

(a) Dataset of our empirical study in Section 3:

One can manually verify the 20k subjects' information used in RQ1 (`20k Subjects Info.xlsx` in `Hero.zip`), and 151 collected DM issues in open-source Golang projects on GitHub (`Empirical Study Dataset.xlsx` in `Hero.zip`), and check the correctness of our categorization of the issues in RQ2&3.

Recently, we also summarized our empirical findings described in Section 3 as a blog, entitled "[A survey on Golang's dependency management modes \(GOPATH and Go Modules\): status quo, problems and challenges](#)". Encouragingly, it attracted official (Google) Golang team's attention and was formally collected into the [Go Wiki Experience Reports Column](#), to help more developer understand the DM issues. The official Golang team's acknowledgement further confirmed the correctness of our empirical results.

(b) Verifying the functional correctness of Hero:

On the "DIAGNOSIS" page of the **Hero** website (<http://www.hero-go.com/>), one can input the name and version number (or hash commit ID) of a Golang project (e.g., project name: `link1st/gowebsocket`, hash commit ID: `03c3c79`) to verify its functional correctness.

Three functionalities can be verified, including: **1)** constructing and visualizing a dependency model for a Golang project under test; **2)** displaying the detailed root causes of identified DM issues; **3)** listing the customized fixing solutions. For more details, one can refer to our [demo](#) provided on the "DIAGNOSIS" page, which better illustrates how to use our Hero.

(c) Verifying the experiment results reported in Section 5.1:

We provide script files and benchmark dataset in the **Benchmark Dataset** folder of **Hero.zip**. For verification, one can run the script to automatically analyze the subjects in a batch mode, and then check the outputted the diagnosis results. For more details, one can refer to **INSTALL** file.

(d) Verifying the experiment results reported in Section 5.2:

On the "ISSUE REPORT" page of the **Hero** website (<http://www.hero-go.com/>), one can check the diagnosis information and the statuses of the 280 real DM issues reported by Hero.

In addition, one can also use the project name and hash commit ID of any subject listed in "ISSUE REPORT" page as inputs, to verify their results on "DIAGNOSIS" page of **Hero**.

A quick start to Hero

First, please go to the online Hero tool via its link (<http://www.hero-go.com/>). Its "DIAGNOSIS" page provides the main function.

■ **Example Golang projects**

Four example Golang projects with four types of DM issues, are provided as follows, which can be used to verify the functional correctness of Hero.

Table 2 example Golang projects with four types of DM issues

Issue Type	Project name	Hash Commit ID
A	kiali/kiali	d0f6507
B.1	gjbae1212/findgs	e259e63
B.2	gookit/cache	540af04
C	github/hub	a1b6bb1

■ **Inputs of Hero**

When a user uses Hero to diagnose issues, two parameters need to be inputted: name and version number of a Golang project released on GitHub. Hero supports two types of project version numbers, i.e., the **version tag number** and the **hash commit ID**. For instance, as shown in Figure 5 and 6, one can input the name and version number of the project to be analyzed on the "DIAGNOSIS" page.

Figure 5. Input the **project name** released on GitHub

Figure 6. Input the **version number /hash commit ID** of the project to be analyzed

Alternatively, as shown in Figure 7, a user can also input the **version tag number** of the project to be analyzed.

Figure 7. Input the version tag number of the project to be analyzed

■ Constructing and visualizing a dependency model & diagnosing DM issues

On the "DIAGNOSIS" page, when a user inputs the name and version number of a Golang project released on GitHub and presses the "Start" button, Hero will construct and display a dependency model of the project under test. From the dependency model, as shown in Figure 8, a user can check the dependency relationships among the client project's downstream and upstream projects and their corresponding library-referencing modes. In addition, based on the constructed dependency model, Hero can diagnose the DM issues and provide their detailed **root causes** and customized **fixing solutions** with analyses of potential benefits and consequences incurring to the ecosystem if certain fixing solutions are taken, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 8. Constructing and visualizing a dependency model

Root cause	Suggested solutions
<p>ISSUE Type A : (This issue report warns you against the possible problems when you try to upgrade the following dependencies.) <i>kiail/kiail</i> is module-unaware, and depends on projects: <i>jaegertracing/jaeger</i>, <i>.prometheus/client_golang</i>, <i>.prometheus/client_golang</i>. Build errors will occur when upgrading these upstream projects, because these projects:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add Go modules in the recent versions. 2. Comply with the specification of "Releasing Modules for v2 or higher" available in the Modules documentation. 3. Have the virtual paths with version suffixes (i.e., v2+), which cannot identified by the module-unaware projects using legacy Golang versions or dependency manage tools (e.g., dep, glide, govendor, etc.). <p>See golang/dep#1962 golang/dep#2139.</p>	<p>1. Migrate to Go Modules. Benefit: This solution encourages migration from GOPATH to Go Modules. (Go Modules is the general trend of ecosystem. Migrating to Go Modules is a good choice for you to get a better upgrade package experience.) Cost: This solution will break compatibility with downstream projects without module awareness. (Migrating to modules will be accompanied by the introduction of virtual paths. Thus the module-unaware downstream projects might get build errors.) [*] You can see which module-unaware downstream projects will be affected: (6 module-unaware users, e.g., gridgentoo/kiail, jotak/k-charted-server, jshaughn/kiail-org-kiail) LINK</p> <p>2. Maintain v2+ libraries in Go Modules in your Vendor directory rather than reference them by virtual import paths. Manually download the dependencies into your vendor directory and do compatibility dispose(Materialize the virtual path or Delete the virtual part of the path). Benefit: Making a copy of libraries in your Vendor directory can avoid virtual import paths. Cost: Your downstream module unaware projects have to make a copy of your Vendor directory, causing extra maintenance overhead to downstream projects. Meanwhile, as the import paths have different meanings for module aware projects and module unaware projects, materializing the virtual path is a better way to solve the issue, while ensuring compatibility with downstream module users. Deleting the virtual part of the path will hurt your downstream</p>

Figure 9. Providing their detailed root causes and customized fixing solutions